
TEACHER PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT CYCLE BASED ON EMPLOYEE'S TARGET

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to know how teacher performance management as a continuous performance process to equalize individual teacher goals and educational institutions also teacher performance series starting from the planning, implementation and evaluation phase which are oriented to minimum work standards in order to obtain income eligibility, benefits, and promotion or rank only which resulting in the performance of teachers dwelling on matters of an administrative nature and setting aside performance processes that produce output and outcome according to the objectives of educational institutions. This research used a qualitative research design by concerning to a phenomenon approach. Data collection techniques used by some steps such as observation, interviews and documentation. Data analysis included single site analysis and cross-site analysis with data analysis techniques; data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions. This research produced four main findings among others; first, in pre-cycle stage with preparation for assessment and creating a teacher performance assessment team; second, the phase of planning with the phase of defining, discussing roles, responsibilities, and measurable expectations; third, the phase of coaching with the phase of observation, monitoring, support, feedback, and appreciation; the four phase of the teacher performance management cycle are performance evaluations.

Keywords: Employee Work Targets; Performance Management Cycle; Teacher Performance.

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1. Introduction

Teachers have a strategic role in education and become a foundation in improving the quality of services and educational outcomes. The appearance of Law number 14 of 2005 concerning to Teachers and Lecturers as well as related rules provides teacher standardization as a professional position. Teachers are considered professionals if they are able to carry out their duties according to established standards. The teacher is the part that has the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, evaluating, and evaluating students at the level of early childhood education in formal education, basic education, and secondary education. In carrying out its duty, the teacher applies expertise, skills that meet certain quality standards or norms obtained through professional education. Professional teachers are required to have skills based on deep scientific concepts and theories, emphasize a particular field of expertise in accordance with the field of

their profession, adequate level of teacher education, sensitive to the social impact of the work carried out, and in line with the dynamics of life (Kunandar, 2014, P. 46).

The responsibility charged to the teacher is measured by considering the quality and quantity in the form of work result (A.P. Mangkunegara, 2011, P. 67). In addition, performance can also be interpreted as a result and effort of a person that is achieved by the existence of abilities and actions in certain situations. Performance is related to the quality of a person in doing work. A person's performance is also accompanied by the quality or quantity of the work. In teacher case, performance is often associated with questions about what teachers do in class, for students and schools, the contribution of teachers to students and educational institutions where they work. Teachers who have good performance are considered as professional and have professional knowledge also abilities (Supardi, 2014, p. 70). Regarding with productive teachers, A.D. Timpe states (Sutikno, 2009,p. 113) teachers who have high performance are, and their characteristics such as; (1) have thought intelligence and can learn about the conditions quickly; (2) have professional competence; (3) have high creativity and innovation; (4) understand and master the work; (5) learn and cleverly use logic and organize work efficiently; (6) always strive to make improvements; (7) considered valuable by the supervisor; (8) have good achievements; and (9) always strive to improve their abilities.

Some people consider that this teacher performance appraisal to be a shape of punishment toward the ability of teachers, especially those who already have professional certificates. In fact, this assumption is not true. Teacher performance assessment is carried out to improve the mastery of teacher competency and develop professional performance. In addition, the results of the teacher's performance appraisal are also needed for promotion and the class of teachers concerned. Work done with a certain position while doing work with perceptions of attitude and behavior is a career understanding. This has become a systematic pattern in developing positions and the process of upgrading a teacher position. The main drivers of employee work readiness depend on the position or career that must be developed with the interaction of individual and organizational competencies (Nia, 2017: 82).

The teacher's performance in order to achieve good and structured conditions is inseparable from the way of management managed both the supervisor and the teacher concerned. Performance management is related with planning, implementing, assessment, and evaluating the performance. This process is the route of teacher performance management.

The performance of teachers in *Madrasah* is the main responsibility of the headmaster. The head of *Madrasah* fosters his teacher so that getting better achievement. The head of *Madrasah* as a leader in the education unit is required to be able to realize the objectives that have been determined. Success in developing teacher performance is largely determined by the head of *Madrasah* since the planning, implementation, supervision, control and alignment of all educational resources. The main task of teacher is to plan learning, carry out learning, doing evaluation and assessment, make improvements also enrich learning. While the task of developing the professional profession relates to personal competencies including the activities of scientific forums, conducting research, scientific publications, and implementing learning innovations. In addition, the supported tasks of teacher are related to student coaching, professional membership, and learning evaluation activities.

Since the legal regulations of the Head Republic of Indonesia State Civil Service Agency Number 1 of 2013 concerning to the implementation Provisions of Government Regulation Number 46 of 2011 talking about Civil Servants Job Performance Assessments including teachers who are Civil Servants, managing teacher performance by using Employee Performance Target patterns. Teacher performance based on employee work goals does not only focus on the main tasks of the teacher but includes three things, namely the performance of the main teacher according to their main tasks, teacher performance in professional development, and teacher performance in supporting their main task duties. *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* as an educational institution under the auspices of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia which is the same as the shelter primary school of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia. Educational institutions as organizations certainly have a work system that regulates governance in *Madrasah* management, finance, infrastructure, curriculum and management of the education process. One standard of education is the standard of teaching and education personnel in its management including recruitment systems, structuring of teaching staff according to qualifications, work arrangement according to competence, performance appraisal, performance monitoring, performance evaluation, and performance improvement in order to improve the quality of educators in educational institutions. *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* as an Islamic education institution under the auspices of the Ministry of Religion is guided by 8 education standards determined by the government, one of which is the management of educators and education personnel.

State Civil Service Agency regulations on employee work achievement are applied in all government agencies. Likewise the ministry of religion applied it to structural and functional employees including among civil servant teachers. State *Madrasah* are educational institutions organized by the government and under the guidance of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. In Trenggalek district, there are only two state *Madrasah* schools under, namely *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1 and 2. Both *Madrasah* apply employee performance appraisals based on employee work goals. Management of employee work through the early stage is that planning, observation, and assessment at the end of the year.

The teacher performance management system in Trenggalek 1 and 2 State *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* regarding with teacher management and work uses performance references based on employee performance targets set by the government as a means of achieving employee performance. To address this matter, the head of *Madrasah* has formed a teacher performance evaluation team and a continuous professional development team as outlined in the decision letter of *Madrasah* head. The team is tasked with coordinating the work procedures of the teacher starting from the formulation of work forms, performance measurement, performance appraisal, planning and implementing development activities for teachers who are still experiencing lack of performance aspects, besides that, open development for teachers who wish to add to their scientific repertoire. Teacher performance appraisal is oriented to the teacher's obligation to carry out their duties with the formative and summative assessment process in the form of teacher competence. While the assessment of teacher performance with the employee work target pattern is oriented to the obligation of each civil servant teacher with a form of portfolio assessment furthermore it can be billed and carried out at the end of the year.

Performance management defines as a systematic process to improve organizational performance by developing individual and team performance as a means of getting better results by understanding and managing performance within an agreed framework regarding with planned goals, standards and competency requirements. The performance management cycle is the sequence of performance processes and activities carried out sequentially and continuously with the core of achieving the expected results (performance). According to Armstrong (2009: 12) performance management is “Performance management can be defined as systematic process improving organizational by developing the performance individuals and teams. It is a mean of getting result from organization, teams and individuals by understanding and managing performance within an agreed frame work of planned goal, standard an competence requirements”.

Performance has defined as a result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee while carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Teacher’s performance is interpreted as work results in the quality and quantity that a teacher achieves in his duties according to his responsibilities and functions. In addition, performance improvement defines as a process of transforming current performance conditions towards better performance conditions in the future (Wibowo, 2014: 243). Steps to improve teacher performance are a process of improving teacher performance to improve conditions for better performance. The process of improving teacher performance is carried out with continuous professional development and training to upgrade teacher performance with the aim of achieving teacher professionalism.

Based on various explanations above, performance management defines as a series of performance both in organizations, groups, and individuals with various efforts to improve in order to achieve organizational goals that have been previously set in a certain period of time. Performance management is very necessary in order to meet the standards of the results determined by the organization through the performance of the organization. Regarding teacher performance management, it has been defined as a management process designed to link organizational goals with individual teacher interests so as to ensure that between teacher and individual goals are the same. In this case the teacher’s performance management is oriented on how to manage the work of the teacher to achieve the targets and results expected by the educational institution.

Management of teacher performance is closely related to the implementation of work in schools or *Madrrasah*. The teacher carries out his duties as a form of responsibility both in terms of quantity and quality. His tasks include making learning planning, classroom learning, assessment and evaluation, and steps to improve and enrich the results of student learning evaluation. The success of teacher in carrying out his duties and the role of his profession is a measurement of performance achieved. This shows the work ethic and integrity of the teacher according to the professionalism he carries on. Performance management is an integrated process that unites power and supports organizational performance with workforce management. The benefits of performance management are oriented towards increasing individual and organizational performance in phases of inventorying capabilities and non-financial rewards for staff, seeking the basis for helping employees with low performance, used to develop individuals, support superior leadership, process motivation and recycle performance activities (Amstrong, 2006: 11).

Regarding to the performance management cycle based on Seeker and Wilson (Madyan, Al Aslah, 2018, p. 205) the performance management cycle includes several phases, namely the preparation of work design, supervision and direction, and assessment. The phases of work design include assignment of assignments, explanation of employee positions, willingness to work and measurement of ability. Phases of supervision include observation, monitoring the process of performance, guidance and direction, providing motivation and response to the leadership. Phases of assessment include measuring the results of work achieved and rearranging the work mechanism of the following year repeatedly.

Figure 1: source, Ramelan,2000: 5

Performance management has an interest toward everyone involved in the organization which is not only the leadership needs. Performance management as an integrated process that consolidates goal setting, performance assessment, and development into a single system with orientation to ensure employee performance supports the company (Leena & Prusty, 2012: 3). The performance management process with a holistic approach to managing performance is in the interest of everyone within organization but it does not become a comprehensive practice. Performance management is related to the commitment of workers to the problem of managing organizational resources as inputs, implementation processes, performance results, and the impact of performance.

2. Planning Phase

The planning phase as a form of agreement between workers and managers who working together to plan what must be done by workers in the coming year, it defines how performance must be measured, identified and planned to overcome obstacles and gain mutual understanding of work (Wibowo, 2014: 58). Work design has become the basis for leaders and subordinates in implementing performance within organizations. Implementation is the practice of planning in the form of factual activities. During the implementation process, a manager has an important task to mobilize its members. An objective structured assessment system has the role of increasing work motivation and supporting the reward system that is implemented by the institution and has an impact on increasing employee productivity (Dadson, Margaret & Patrick, 2014: 194).

Thomas S. Bateman and Scott A. Snell stated that the steps in making a good plan that is first is situational analysis, followed by the second with alternative goals and plans, the next step is the goal and plan evaluation, the fourth stage is the goal and plan selection, then will be ended by the implementation (Thomas S. Bateman and Scott A. Snell, 2014, e 10, p. 118-121). Work agreements establish expectations of the work that must be done, the results achieved and the attributes and competencies needed to achieve these results. Determination of roles determines individual responsibilities in achieving output, abilities, skills and behavior in carrying out work according to adherence (Qureshi, 2010: 1857). Dharma said that the performance expectation aspect is crucial in making performance agreements including (a) job descriptions must be carried out in the form of key result areas, (b) performance targets and standards, (c) performance indicators and indicators, (d) attributes and competencies, and (e) organizational requirements and basic values (Surya Dharma, 2013: 68). Individual planning models develop work plans for each member by considering the skills, knowledge, and abilities they have. Setting goal is the main thing in planning performance and agreement phases, also represents the process itself (Mariahermel, 2015: 277). The work plan also details the responsibilities of each member needed to achieve the work group's goals and techniques. Components of individual work plans include job descriptions, work objectives, and performance action plans (Karen R Seeker and Joe B Wilson, 2000: 12). Management based on goals or objectives is the assessment of employees with the process of setting common goals between leaders and subordinates on the basis of the participation of each individual (Zulystiawati, 2014: 127)

3. Coaching

Coaching defines as the process of monitoring, observing, and monitoring the performance of subordinates according to their respective duties (Ivancevich, 2008: 46). In the performance management cycle, the teacher coaching phase is guided and developed even encourages or directs their efforts through support, feedback, and appreciation. The work plan agreement between the leadership and subordinates is the implementation of planning in the form of factual activities. During the implementation process a manager has an important task to mobilize its members. Coaching according (Malthis, R.L & Jackson, 2012, p.112) as a form of achieving organizational goals through certain competencies of each individual organized, so that supervision in the form of guidance becomes a thing that is done for the sake of implementing organizational goals both special and general. Direction is an effort to create a dynamic, healthy working atmosphere so that performance is more effective and efficient. Some activities in the function of directing: guiding and motivating workers to be able to work effectively and efficiently, give assignments and explain regularly about work, and explain all policies that have been set.

Actually, Coaching becomes a continuous series of performance which in this case consider as a process of improving employee work. Implementing effective performance measurements for any organization requires an effective performance measurement system. It is the system that will monitor, evaluate, and determine success in achieving the goals and performance targets that have been measured. The performance management system enables management of organizations and stakeholders to track performance at certain times and routine interventions to assess performance (Andrew, 2014: 4). Furthermore, Coaching is the stage of developing and providing employee motivation to achieve peak performance. Coaching is part of the ongoing

cycle of planning, coaching, evaluating, and measuring performance in a performance management system activity that continues to roll out every year in a cycle that is avenue for continuous learning by all organizational human resources. Coaching also defines as a valuable effort to help others achieve high performance (Bill Foster and Karen R. Seeker, 2010: 1).

Bill Foster and Karen R. Seeker stated that there are four things that are part of the model of employee coaching being the responsibility of a leader among others; (1) monitor employee performance. This first step is for managers to use materials from the planning process which include: employee job descriptions, performance targets, and performance action plans to find out the roles, responsibilities, actions, and measurements that have been agreed upon between the manager and employees which are the basis for determining that year's performance. Managers use these materials observe employee performance, then document behavior that indicates whether success or failure in carrying out their obligations. (2) Diagnosing performance improvement needs. In this part, by monitoring employee behavior managers can assess whether employee behavior meets performance goals, exceeds, or it does not meet any expectations. If the employee's behavior does not meet expectations this context usually appears in four areas, namely knowledge, skills, motivation, and self-confidence. These four fields are factors that shape the competency of an employee. (3) Establishing the way to improve the situation. After the performance improvement demands are identified, the manager needs to determine the type of direction or support and then determine what the employee needs. For example, some considerations in form of questions such as *what should be done by employees, how to do it, and when to do it*. In this context, it is better for managers to determine what employees need to be discussed with the employees concerned. (4) Conveying the constructive feedback. Giving feedback is a continuous process. Therefore, it must be prepared and delivered constructively and carefully, so that the feedback can be understood by the employees concerned. What is very important is trying as much as possible the direction or support of the manager of the employee can help employees or not. If you succeed in helping the employee, respect the efforts of the employee to improve that performance and celebrate with him. (Bill Foster and Karen R. Seeker, 2010: 12).

Figure 2: Coaching to employee performance (Bill Foster dan Karen R. Seeker, 2010)

Educational organizations strive to build performance through increasing employee competencies, empowering employees, providing balanced and proportional compensation programmed and sustainable employee development through performance monitoring, diagnosing repair needs, establishing ways to improve, and conveying constructive feedback that leads to improve performance employees and organizations. Principal and teacher communication as a form of coaching and working together to share information about problem solving, performance improvement and progress, and factors that do not support performance. The skill in finding and overcoming problems are important things of communication that are built by the principal.

4. Evaluation Phase

To find out the effectiveness and efficiency of a manager's plan is a must to conduct an evaluation. Performance evaluation is the process of evaluating workers on various dimensions related to work (John W. Newstrom and Keith Davis, 2009: 175). Performance evaluation defines as the process of evaluating workers on various dimensions related to work. Performance evaluation assesses and evaluates individual performance and becomes an important stage of system performance. Leaders obtain data and achievements of subordinates' performance which both can be through self-assessment and supervisor's assessment. In order for performance evaluation to get good results, the leader reviews due to it can be an illustration of the condition of employee performance so that it can be one of the information for performance evaluation. The implications of performance evaluation include evaluating goals and objectives, evaluating performance plans, evaluating work environments, evaluating performance processes, evaluating performance measurements, and evaluating results (Robert Kreitner and Angelo Kinicki, 2010: 300). The results of subordinate performance can be seen from the results of the assessment obtained during the activity. Research guidance is carried out at the end of the activity based on a predetermined time. The assessment is performed to know the level of ability of employees, in this case is referred to the teacher. In addition, the assessment is also performed to show the level of cooperation among teachers, superiors, and educational institutions. The assessment that has been carried out is the basis for determining the steps to improve and develop teacher performance.

The target of Employee Work is the work target that will be carried out by civil servants for one year. Moreover, in this case Target of Employee Work also categorizes as a form of employment contract between civil servants and direct superiors. On the basis of Employee Work Objectives that have been self-made by civil servants and approved by direct superiors as appraisers, then the supervisor can directly assess the employee's work performance, by comparing the target or work contract in the employee's work target with the reality of work achieved in one year. The employee's work target is a written statement from the employee about the performance that must be achieved by pouring performance planning with an output orientation that is comparable to the performance planning of him-self. Individual work goals are statements of individuals in their fields of work with the target orientation of the results they will achieve. Dedi stated that the components of individual work targets included a description of the field of work to be carried out, type of work (quantity and quality of work standards), time of achievement and targeted work results compared to the type of work, and the time also cost of completing the work (Dedi Rianto Rahadi, 2010: 116).

The individual teacher's work target indicators are based on the ministerial regulation on the utilization of state apparatus and bureaucracy number 16 of 2009 concerning to teacher functional positions and their credit numbers include three things among others; 1) learning assignments, 2) professional development, and 3) supporting teaching and learning activities. The design of employee performance evaluation in this context is individual teachers who are inseparable from teacher competency standards. Design of individual performance appraisal systems with processes; (a) the beginning of the work year or the work calendar for each institution / educational institution plans performance targets by making a work contract agreed upon by the individual and his / her supervisor, (b) the contents of the employment contract are monitored and assessed part-time at the beginning of the work year with a formative assessment system and the end of the work calendar with summative assessment, (c) the work contract is observed and monitored in two phases, namely the formative and summative phases, (d) performance appraisal by comparing individual planning entries for each item described in the planned work with the physical results achieved during the assessment period of the work calendar, then scoring the results of work with the predicate of assessment according to the agreed standards and determined by the organization, (e) statement of performance results is poured in the form of an assessment by pouring in the value of each performance item and giving the predicate or qualification of the results achieved, (f) the end of the assessment, there is an evaluation of the shortcomings of individuals who give individual demands to participate in the activities of enhancing, empowering and developing individual performance so that future improvements in matters can meet the planned targets.

Teacher performance assessment defines as the process of analyzing and evaluating the implementation and results of the teacher's work in carrying out his roles and functions professionally. Teacher performance assessments becomes the basis for setting teacher credit numbers for one year of performance and capital for continuing professional development for teachers according to the results accordance to the assessment. The assessment time for teacher performance assessment activities divides as two, namely formative assessment (initial) and summative assessment (end of year). The aspect of teacher performance appraisal includes each item of the main task in developing a career, title and position.

While the work target of the employee for the teacher defines as a work plan and targets to be achieved by civil servant teachers who are compiled and agreed upon between employees and direct supervisors of employees. Employee work targets are made at the beginning of the year, namely in January and if it has been approved by the superiors with the form of the final target sheet then it will be determined to be measured within one year and assessed at the end of the year in December of that year. Employee work targets are mandatory for civil servants, including teachers of civil servants, if the teacher is proven to not make the work target of the employee, then he will be sanctioned according to the applicable provisions. The assessment of employee work targets includes aspects of quantity, quality, time and cost according to task characteristics relevant civil servants. If the civil servant is a teacher, the four aspects adjust according to his duties as a teacher.

5. Research Method

To answer the research question, this type of research uses qualitative design which adopts from the model of Miles & Huberman (2014, p.10). The study was conducted at the State Islamic Elementary School *Madrasah* Trenggalek as the location of the research. The object of the research focused on State Islamic schools in the area. The intended *Madrasah(s)* are Trenggalek 1 and 2 State *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah*. The unit of analysis used in this study is institutional. Considering this research is focused on Trenggalek State *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* teachers, in detail the analysis is the implementation of the duties and functions of teachers in two states *Madrasah* in that area.

In this study the main data sources are the words and actions of principals and teachers at Trenggalek State *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah*. Then, data will be collected through observations, interviews, and library research related *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* to the implementation of teacher duties. In addition, data from *Madrasah's* supervisor is also needed as additional data which is able to provide an overview of the implementation of teacher duties in the state secondary *Madrasah*.

The measurement of the data validity is done through triangulation, which is to do validation toward the research data that has been obtained in the field. Data analysis is done by looking for and systematically compiling data obtained from interviews, field notes, and other materials, so that they can be easily understood, and their findings can be informed to others (Sugiyono, 2015, p. 334)

6. Findings

The performance management cycle in Trenggalek 1 and 2 *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* uses the planning phase (defining, discussing roles, responsibilities and measurable expectations), the coaching phase (observation, support, feedback and appreciation), and evaluation phase.

7. Planning Phase

Teacher performance planning based on employee work targets which can be observed in Trenggalek 1 State *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* site is structuring teacher assignments, determining teacher achievement targets, supervisor communication and preparatory subordinate performance, and teacher moral responsibility. Teacher task management uses operational standard processes that guide the determination of position and duties assigned by the teacher, standard assignments and teacher teaching burdens require the allocation of teacher needs based on student ratio, suitability of teacher education qualifications with fields that are provided by a teacher-certified teacher standard is declared as appropriate or linear even though the teacher's education qualifications are not in accordance with the field being administered, and the eligibility status is accepted by the Ministry of Religion's Management System of Educators and Education Personnel Management System data, teachers who fulfill the requirements are entitled to carry out their duties according to the allocation of class teachers, Islamic Education, Field of Mathematics Studies, Sports Education, and the Field of Arabic Language Studies. The proper

status of the sympathetic system is highly preferred due to this status is related to the welfare of the teacher in the form of a professional allowance.

Discussion about the role of teacher in the form of determining the achievement of performance targets in one year relates with the writing of a work plan on the employee work target sheet every January. Teachers are given signs of target preparation in a minimum of a year assessment and preparation of performance targets based on the teacher's credit number needs for that year. Moral responsibility is the basis for preparing a work plan, not just aborting obligations, but there are individual demands from teachers to meet their own set targets.

Two-ways communication between superiors and teachers is applied before legalization of the work target sheet aimed at measuring oneself for the teacher to use self-evaluation so that teacher is expected to meet the performance targets well and according to the performance plan. Communication is carried out in a closed manner especially for the teacher who concern with his superior so that the teacher is given a space of freedom to convey his work plan and the obstacles he faces. The purpose of self-evaluation before the validation of the worksheet is to avoid practices that are quite good in planning but not realized. Whereas on the site of State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 2, this performance planning is almost same as State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1, namely the assignment of tasks and the teacher's role using the feasibility sympathy system and rules to be the main basis, discussion about the roles by determining performance targets at the beginning and self-evaluation teacher before the achievement plan is authorized by the superior.

8. Coaching

Coaching on teacher performance based on employee work targets observed in the State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1 is observation of performance, support, feedback, and appreciation. The performance observation as a process of evaluating the performance toward the teacher in using the reference work sheet of the employee's work had been prepared earlier in the year. The performance assessment of the teacher's main tasks includes pedagogical competencies, personality competencies, social competencies, and professional competencies. The four components are broken down into 14 competency assessments of teacher performance including the ability of the students' characteristics, the ability of learning theory and the principles of learning that educate, the ability to develop curriculum, educating learning abilities, the ability to develop potential students, communication skills with students, the ability to assess and evaluate, the ability to act in accordance with religious norms, law, social and national culture, to show an adult and exemplary person, work ethic, high responsibility, pride in being a teacher, being inclusive, acting objectively, and not being discriminatory, communication with fellow teachers, education staff, parents, students, and the community, mastery of material abilities, structure, scientific concepts and mindsets that support the subjects taught, and the ability to develop professionalism through reflective actions.

Within the process of performance observation is done through instruments and indicators of observation pre, middle, and post observation. The observation process is carried out by the teacher's performance assessment team used direct approach to the class type the learning process, interview with the teacher, and check the completeness of documents that teacher has.

Teacher performance appraisal based on employee work objectives is carried out in two phases, namely the formative stage (within January to June) and the formative stage (within July to December), which the results are combined into the final value of performance in December. If at the end of the assessment the teacher has not met the target according to the plan automatically the achievement value will go down to the predicate below or less. This causes teachers to experience difficulties in meeting their targets due to adjustments in the new curriculum relating to learning planning, learning administration, and assessment in the adaptation process, and teachers are still having difficulty in making written works and innovative works.

Support provided to cover the lack of performance assessment team carried out individual consultation forums and group consultations according to the substance of the problem. The existence of weekly meeting activities as a vehicle for communication between teachers and superiors is carried out from Monday to Thursday at each student's return hour until the deadline for working hours. The material comes up about the substance learning plan, assessment, writing, and innovative works is guided directly by the performance assessment team of State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1 teachers. Feedback efforts in the form of awards for teachers who perform well in *Madrasah* provide written awards, assistance with further study, and promotion. Whereas site 2 in State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 2, this performance coaching is similar to State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1, namely the observation or performance appraisal process using two phases, the formative stage, and the summative stage which results are merged into the final score in December which is an assessment team set by the head of *Madrasah*, the procedure of observation uses instructors and indicators both before, in the process, and after observation. State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 2 provides encouragement to teachers who experience difficulties in individual consultation forums and have not carried out weekly activities to consult in a persuasive group of problems faced by the teacher. Support in the form of awards is still in written awards, and promotion through an assessment system by the Ministry of Religion does not yet have an award program in the form of further study fees.

9. Performance Evaluation

Performance evaluation as the culmination of performance appraisal, work evaluation based on employee work targets observed in State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1 is held in December. Each teacher collects physical files according to the work target sheet, each in the form of physical evidence of the teacher's main task, physical evidence of self-development, physical evidence of scientific publications, and other supporting physical evidence. The assessment team analyzes the collected physical evidence and provides an assessment in the form of a sheet of teacher performance appraisal results and the acquisition of credit figures for the performance of the teacher's main tasks. The results of the teacher's main task performance assessment are entered into the achievement sheet of the employee's work target results by mentioning the value of the credit number, quality of achievement, and quantity of the file achieved.

Whereas self-development assessment, scientific publications, innovative works, and other supporting tasks refer to the assessment guidelines determined by *Madrasah* and the results are contained in the performance achievement measurement sheet by mentioning the quantity

achieved, the results of the credit numbers, and the quality of the achievements. All the assessment results of the teacher's main tasks, self-development, scientific publications, innovative work, and other supporting tasks are published in the form of a measurement sheet for the achievement of work targets authorized by superiors. Performance improvement is a program for the preparation of improvement activities needed by teachers in State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1 according to the analysis results of teacher performance assessments, and the improvement program becomes the activity agenda for the following year.

In State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 2, performance evaluation and work improvement are almost the same as Trenggalek State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1, which is in December collects all physical files starting from the teacher's main tasks, self-development, scientific publications, innovative works, and other supporters to be analyzed and assessed by *Madrasah* level teacher performance assessment team and the results of measurement are published in the form of employee work target measurement sheets and authorized by superiors. The preparation of a performance improvement program is almost same as State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1, which is preparing the needed improvement program by adjusting *Madrasah* budget.

The teacher performance assessment and continuing professional development team were legalized by *Madrasah* head as a work team in State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1 and State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 2 played a role in case the effectiveness of teacher performance management process starting from the planning, coaching and evaluation phases. The teacher's performance appraisal team becomes the executor of the principal's task and as an evaluator of teacher assignments on the basis of Employee Work Objectives which has an impact in improving teacher performance. Besides that the communication that was built between the leadership and the teacher on the site 1 State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 1 and site 2 State of *Madrasah Ibtidaiyah* Trenggalek 2 through the teacher performance appraisal team and continuous professional development and the creation of a harmonious climate of performance and mutual assistance between one teacher and others.

10. Conclusion

Based on the description and results data analysis of interview, observations and document studies, it can be concluded that the teacher performance management cycle is based on employee work goals through several phases among others (1) pre-cycle (preparation), (2) planning (3) production (4) evaluation creates the effectiveness of teacher performance management. The findings of this study empower and support the Seeker and Wilson performance management cycle theory that performance management goes which is done by three cycles, namely (1) the planning phase through the defining phase, the role discussion phase, the expectation phase, and the discussion phase, (2) the phases through observation phase, monitoring phase, support phase, feedback phase, and award phase, and (3) evaluation phase through work evaluation phase and work development phase. In this study also found an indication of the important role of the teacher performance assessment team worked by doing the assisting, facilitating, observing, monitoring, assessing and establishing effective two-way communication between teachers and superiors as long as teacher performance management is

carried out. In teacher performance management, *Madrasah* principals have an important role in the regulation of teacher performance systems within educational institutions.

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